

Equations^d relating light trap catches of rice-feeding insects to distance from an isolated field, and estimated dispersal distances. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, Jan-Feb 1982.

	YSB males	YSB females	<i>P. fluctuosalis</i>	<i>N. aenescens</i>
Period	19/1 - 16/2	19/1 - 16/2	19/1 - 12/2	19/11 - 8/2
Best-fitting equation	$Y = 87.0 - 5.74 \ln(X + 0.5)$	$Y = 48.1 + 33.0 \ln(X + 0.5) - 2.72 \ln(X + 0.5)^2$	$Y = 11.0 \exp(-0.002 X)$	$Y = 6.83 \exp(-0.003 X)$
F	9.45*	11.7*	4.77*	5.08*
R ² 0.53		0.59	0.27	0.39
Equation corrected for background density	$Y = 40.0 - 5.74 \ln(X + 0.5)$	$Y = 43.6 + 33.0 \ln(X + 0.5) - 2.72 \ln(X + 0.5)^2$	$Y = 8.59 \exp(-0.003 X)$	$Y = 6.35 \exp(-0.006 X)$
R ² 0.53	0.59		0.29	0.39
Estimated dispersal distances (km):				
50% of population	0.46	0.76	0.64	0.27
80% of population	0.70	1.10	1.10	0.47

^a Y = total catch during the indicated period, X = distance from the field edge. * = P < 0.05. YSB = yellow stem borer.

Dispersal may have been underestimated because the transects were oriented to the prevailing wind. On the other hand, dispersal from a field planted in synchrony with surrounding areas

probably would have been lower, because insects would fly over potential habitat rather than over barren ground. Dispersal estimates are sensitive to the assumed background density, but catches at the

Catch of YSB in kerosene light traps 19 Jan-16 Feb 1982, in relation to distance from the edge of an isolated field planted out of season. The curve is the uncorrected equation given in the table.

traps used to calculate background density were low and uniform for all but YSB males.

The median dispersal distances we found are similar to indices of dispersal derived from the correlation of seasonal abundance as measured in light traps, and the duration of the rice crop in the vicinity (described elsewhere). ■

Rice yellow stem borer (YSB) egg deposition preferences

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We studied preference of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) moths for egg deposition on deepwater rice (DWR) during the first week of Jul 1988. YSB moth populations were very high in Rajbari, Gazipur (a DWR research site). We counted the egg masses on four randomly selected lines out of 12, each 5 m long, in a regional yield trial.

BR4112-2B-6 and DWC-B-184 had significantly fewer egg masses (Table 1). Plant height, leaf blade width, and foliage color did not correlate with number of egg masses.

In 1989, we tested apparent nonpreference for egg deposition on these DWR entries in a pot experiment in the nethouse, in a completely randomized design with eight replications. Three of the less preferred and two of the highly preferred entries were exposed for 2 d at maximum tillering to about 300 female moths. Egg masses deposited and tiller

Table 1. Yellow stem borer egg masses deposited on deepwater rice^a entries at early elongation stage. Rajbari, Gazipur, Bangladesh, July 1988.

Line	Replications (no.)	Foliage color	Plant height (cm)	Leaf blade width (mm)	Egg mass density ^b (no./4 rows)
BR4112-2B-6	3	Pale green	128.9	7.8	1.0 e
DWC-B-184	3	Deep green	139.8	8.7	1.3 e
Habiganj Aman II	3	Pale green	118.3	6.5	2.7 de
BR311-B-5-4	4	Pale green	108.7	6.5	3.0 cde
Sadapankaich	4	Pale green	115.2	6.8	3.2 cde
BR516-48-3	3	Green	131.4	7.2	3.3 bcde
BR308-B-2-4	4	Green	115.5	6.1	3.5 bcde
Kartiksail	4	Green	109.0	7.9	3.5 bcde
BR683-65-4-1-1 (c)	3	Pale green	108.8	6.6	3.7 bcde
DWC-B-14-1-x-6	4	Green	107.7	6.3	3.7 bcde
Habiganj Aman I	4	Pale green	110.9	6.2	3.7 bcde
BR683-65-4-1-1 (M)	3	Deep green	99.4	8.1	4.0 bcde
BR4112-2B-9	3	Green	130.4	6.7	4.0 bcde
Habiganj Aman IV	4	Green	105.9	6.4	4.7 bcd
Kartiksail-HR8	4	Green	105.4	6.4	5.0 bcd
BR306-B-3-2-HR46	3	Green	136.4	6.8	5.0 bcd
IR11185-0-0-0-88-2	3	Green	133.4	7.1	5.0 bcd
BR224-2B-2-5	4	Green	115.9	6.2	5.2 bcd
BR4112-2B-2	3	Green	126.8	6.7	5.7 bcd
BR4112-2B-7	3	Green	126.6	8.0	6.0 abc
IR33708-2B-1	3	Green	119.4	6.7	6.3 ab
Sadapankaich-HR40	3	Green	122.5	6.6	6.3 ab
BR4112-2B-5	3	Pale green	125.5	7.4	9.0 a

^a Water depth varied from 35 to 55 cm on different plots. ^b Counted on 4 of 12 rows each 5 m long, in 3- × 5-m plots. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

density were counted and average plant height measured.

BR4112-2B-6 and Habiganj Aman II, two of the less preferred entries in the field, had significantly fewer egg masses

than did highly preferred Sadapankaich-HR40 (Table 2). DWC-B-184, which was less preferred in the field, had about the same number of egg masses as the highly preferred entries. ■

Correlations between egg masses and plant height and tiller density were positive and significant. Taller and denser canopies were more preferred for egg deposition. BR4112-2B-6 was least preferred, probably because it had the shortest plants and produced fewer tillers (Table 2).

Leaf blade width and foliage color had no apparent influence on egg deposition. ■

Table 2. Yellow stem borer egg masses deposited on deepwater rice entries in a nethouse. Pot study, BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1989.

Entry	Reaction ^a in 1988	Plant height (cm)	Tiller density (no./pot)	Egg mass density, (no./pot) ^b
Sadapankaich-HR40	HP	73.5	31.3	6.5 a
DWC-B-184	LP	67.0	26.4	5.1 ab
BR4112-2B-5	HP	62.5	21.2	4.0 ab
Habiganj Aman II	LP	54.6	27.2	2.9 b
BR4112-2B-6	LP	46.4	17.4	2.1 b

^a LP = less preferred, HP = highly preferred in the field. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Red stripe, a newly reported disease of rice in Vietnam

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A new disease on rice in the Mekong Delta has the typical symptom of an orange stripe extending from both ends of an oval lesion (Fig. 1).

The lesion usually begins as a small water-soaked yellow spot 0.1-0.3 cm in size. It gradually turns orange-red within 2-3 d. The stripe develops from both ends of the spot, enlarging rapidly under moist, hot conditions, and may extend the entire length of the leaf. Numerous stripes may occur on the same leaf. An infected leaf may die and dry out. Red stripe was also observed on the leaf

sheath. In severe cases, the entire plant may be killed 10-15 d before harvest.

Although the disease has been found on 20-d-old seedlings, it normally is most severe after heading, and can cause 50% yield reduction.

Red stripe was first observed in 1988, when thousands of hectares of rice were affected in Tien Giang Province. Since then, it has been readily found. In the 1990 summer and autumn season, thousands of hectares were affected by the disease. Most promising short-

duration varieties, such as IR64, IR66, IR19660, IR42, MTL 61, and MTL 58, were severely affected.

We isolated *Curvularia lunata* on PDA by culturing 0.1-0.3 cm leaf pieces cut from new spots. We obtained 65-75% fungus 3 to 5 d after culturing.

Inoculum was prepared from cultures grown in the same medium. We inoculated 35- to 45-d-old seedlings by spraying. Inoculated plants were placed in a moist chamber for incubation. Typical lesions appeared 7 d after incubation at 30-32°C, and 15 d after incubation at 26-28°C. Lesions developed on both 35- and 45-d-old seedlings.

When we sectioned diseased tissues, we observed abundant species and mycelium of *C. lunata* in the vascular systems (Fig. 2a,b). ■

1. Typical red stripe lesions on inoculated plants.

2. a) Conidia, conidiophores, mycelia of *C. lunata* PDA culture. b) Spores of *C. lunata* on PDA culture.

Correlations between light trap catches, field populations of yellow stem borer (YSB), and lunar phase

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As part of a larger study on the regional dynamics of rice insect pests, we examined the relationship between YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* catches in small kerosene light traps and populations in adjacent fields.

Nine traps were within a 17,000-ha area of uniform double cropping in Nueva Ecija Province, Philippines, during 1981 wet season. Near the median planting date of surrounding fields, experimental plots of IR52 were